

Cresol Novolak Photoresists: Effect of Compositions, Fractionation and Oligomer concentration on Patterning Potential for Thick Film

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Novolak resists have been widely used in making electronic circuits for ICs and VLSIs at micron and sub-micron levels. As advances in electronic systems with higher speeds, greater functionality, and higher densities have generated requirements for higher sensitivity, higher resolution, and wider process margin for novolak resists. In the present work, with the goal of improving the performance of novolak resists, *m*, *p*-cresol formaldehyde novolak resins have been synthesized by varying the relative amount of cresol monomers. FTIR, ¹HNMR and ¹³CNMR were used to analyze the synthesized resins. GPC was used to determine the molecular weight. Highly fractionated novolak resins (M_w 17000) and low molecular weight novolak resin (M_w 700) at various composition have been investigated for resist formulation to improve resolution and sensitivity. Addition of low molecular weight novolak to highly fractionated novolak enhanced the dissolution rate, fine thin film, image contrast of the resist. Lithographic pattern of resolution 450 nm was observed for cresol novolak of m/p ratio 32/68 and for high fractionated novolak/low mol wt. novolak of 65/35.

Fig: (a) Lithography pattern and (b) Thickness profile of m/p cresol formaldehyde novolak resist

Keywords: Optical lithography, Cresol novolak, fractionated resin, PAC incorporation

References:

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